

Psychological Factors Which Effects The Diet

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find any difficulties in his life. In short, if a person constantly upsets himself, this affects his eating psychologically, and starts to either eat a lot or not eat at all. That is, an eating disorder occurs. This is an undesirable outcome because eating disorders are serious psychological disorders and something needs to be done to treat them.

There is another factor that particularly affects young people. And this factor is so common for teenagers. When you ask something which has changed so quick and unhealthy on their body, he or she would say that the reason is bullying factor. It does not matter you are overweight or underweight, they will always judge you if you're body not like their body.

Especially if you are in high school this situation might be your nightmare. Because in this ages, all the teenagers could want to being the desired one. And when it is not happened, they would effect extremely bad as psychologically. After that, they starts an unhealthy but quick diet program, and this program might destroy them day by day.

1. Introduction

In this article, all of the factors which are effects eating disorders, are examined deeply and are explanatory. All humans have a different psychology. And it could change at any moment. Due to life, everything could happen at any moment for any person. And if it is effective for the person who lives that, this could become a trauma.

Usually, traumatic situations cause diets. Like if there aren't any perception of beauty, everybody would love their body and they also would feel more confident about their body. But there is a thing called "Perception of Beauty", and this makes everybody uncomfortable about their bodies.

As in this sentences in the article, diets are generally concerned with psychology. But there are also different diet varieties which are healthy for the body and for human mentality. Like, you can get a healthy diet program from your nutritionist. He or she would help you with being healthy. However, if you make your own diet program without consulting for expert, this could make your body and psychology worst than previous. For the experts, nobody can make a healthy diet program without consulting with an expert.

Especially, new quick diet programs are increasing nowadays. This trend is influenced by social media platforms.

Assume that you are on a diet, no matter if it is healthy or unhealthy, there would be problems either. The most distinct difficulty is the human mind. You can lose weight, but only if you are ready in your mind. If you are determined about losing weight, you should not care about your progress. Eventually, you can lose weight slowly. When you are ready to lose weight in your brain it means you can get a diet program from experts. Thus, you can healthily lose weight.

Another factor that affects diet psychologically is boredom. When you lose faith in yourself, that you can change your body and lose weight, you not only feel guilty psychologically but also lose your self-confidence.

Being and feeling guilty is one of the most injurious sensations for human psychology. When you suppose that you are guilty about anything, that affects your life and your diet. If you taste that feeling once, you might suppose that you are inadequate and desperate. So according to experts, it would be harder to stick to your diet program than previous.

Almost every human wants to be in the body they want in their dreams. So if they bother themselves with this opinion, that makes them feel worse. Compliance with this diet program is as important as starting the diet program. It is obvious, that finishing this diet must also go through important stages. There are many psychological factors that are effective at every stage of the diet, and these can make dieting easier as well as impossible.

2. Diet Types and Diet Consequences

There are more types of diets in the world than we can count. Perhaps the number of these species may exceed millions. The reason for this is that all diet types, all diet programs are specially prepared for each person. Each person has target differences in terms of weight or health. For this reason, it is the dietitian's first duty to prepare the most appropriate diet program for that person.

Today, especially on social media, many products that are harmful to health, which are sold under the name of diet or for the purposes of losing weight and gaining weight, are advertised

as lies. This is both morally unethical and dangerous to health. Therefore, you should not buy these products without consulting a specialist.

When it comes to diet types, the Atkins diet comes first among the most common diet types in the world. The Zone diet also follows the Atkins diet program. Paleo diet, South Beach diet, Dukan diet and many other diet types have become widespread.

When we look at the results of the diet, the most comfortable result we can see will be weight gain for people who want to gain weight, and weight loss for people who want to lose weight. Of course, this is among the physical effects of the diet. There are positive psychological factors that occur as a result of diet. These are thoughts such as perseverance, determination, patience and self-confidence. When these thoughts settle in the brain, people begin to believe in everything they wonder or want to do in life, and start to trust themselves in these matters. Besides the positive aspects of the diet, there may also be negative aspects. Especially if there is a problem in complying with the diet program and the diet is abandoned, it causes problems such as not feeling enough in the psychology of this person, which is one of the psychological diseases, especially eating disorders.

If the diet is completed with full compliance, but nothing different is felt psychologically or physically, this causes the person to think that he cannot achieve anything that he is incapable of. This is also highly undesirable because it affects people psychologically in a very negative way.

The reason why the diet is not effective here may be due to the fact that there are diet programs that are not prepared according to the right criteria, as well as the fact that a dietitian has not been consulted.

The best thing you can do in such cases is to consult a dietitian or ask your dietitian to change your diet program.

3. Stress and Dealing With Stress

Stress and Dealing With Stress There is nothing worse or worse than being stressed out on a diet. Diets, if they are healthy, are one of the important things that must be done to maintain health, regardless of weight, for human life. Being stressed on a diet is an ordinary thing in

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human life. Regardless, the important thing is not to be stressed, but to reduce stress in a healthy way and learn how to cope with it.

In human life, everything might make humans stressed and dejected. Even a thought can make the person feel bad.

There are many symptoms of stress in human psychology. These stress symptoms can be easily seen by people who are generally conscious of these issues. However, sometimes stress harms people psychologically instead of expressing it specifically. Especially people who have been bullied or vilified about their bodies suddenly start dieting and become obsessed with it without realizing it. This is considered a symptom of an introverted mental illness. Over time, what we call this diet evolves into an eating disorder. But there are also obvious reasons for psychological stress. These are an especially visible distractions and forgetfulness in the person. So when a human is under stress any person can understand that clearly.

Contrary to popular belief, diets are not just for weight loss. You can apply to diets for gaining weight either. There are a million sorts of diets. As the sentences in the article, we can say that the person always should consult with an expert. On social media, the number of users is increasing day by day and these numbers include "Influencers" either. Some of them want to teach how to lose or gain weight quickly, but that is not ethical. Owing to influencers people started not to like their bodies and they started to unhealthy diet methods for psychology and body.

All over the world, dietitians who are experts in their field often change their diet programs from person to person. These diet programs vary according to the person's weight, intended weight, height, and blood values. The reason why these programs are not heavy is that human psychology is often linked to eating habits. Simply, if you replace the coffee you drink in the morning with green tea, this can cause you to have a more negative day. Because of this and other things that affect psychology, dietitians should prepare a program from person to person. In addition, getting the help of a therapist is recommended for people who go on a diet.

With unhealthy diet methods, human psychology is getting worse and worse day by day. Experts are not supportive of that topic. And it seems like they will never agree. That's because the person who tries to give those diet methods could be illiterate about diet programs. So humans do not let themselves illiterate people's thoughts. Because if the person lets himself or

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herself to an illiterate person, her/his psychology could affect badly. And this situation might make the person hit the bottom of the rock.

To prohibit that disease, first, the person should not apply to social media, plus the person should make his mind ready.

The most important thing is having a ready mind to diet. When a human's body and especially his or her mind is not ready for diet programs, the result would be probably failed. Both physically and mentally. And this might cause some bad consequences which are not wanted. Instead of experiencing that bad thing, the person should be ready thus nothing bad would happen to the person. Because these consequences are not just about their body, it is also concerned about human psychology. This non - wanted psychological consequences might cause everything. Like eating disorders, depression, bipolar disorders, mood changes, and a lot of diseases in psychology.

However, all of those diseases have a solution. Some people get that disease over with speaking and some people are focused on something different for making their minds clean. But when they recognize that they have a disease because of wrong diet methods, that person would have psychological help before that disease make that person's psychology worse.

Although every psychologist has their solution methods, they all come to the same door. There are many solutions in psychology, but they all provide the same thing. Of course, the methods applied according to each disease and the degree of that disease also vary. For example, there are people who may start to feel inadequate in some matters while following the diet program. The reasons for these people to feel inadequate may be different. One person may follow this diet to gain weight, while another may apply it to lose weight. Therefore, although the cause of the problem is common, situations may vary.

For example, while a person might be want to more skinny but also the other person might gain weight at the same time, so they both want to find a solution to their weight. If they would not find that solution, their diet program would make worse their psychology. So that is why there is some kind of factors that affects the diet.

We can call the process of consciously losing or gaining weight a diet. However, people who are going through psychologically difficult times can change their eating habits in order to

overcome their trauma, and unknowingly, harm situations that can reach important dimensions related to their own psychology can be revealed.

Especially people who do not have the opportunity to face their trauma or who are afraid to face their traumas close themselves in. And they give themselves to food. This situation can cause unhealthy weight gain in them, in addition, unless this situation is taken under control, it can reach serious psychological and physical diseases. At the same time, some people, on the contrary, may distance themselves from eating altogether. This situation causes great diseases in them. Actually, they both mean the same thing. Both are symptoms of an eating disorder. In short, diet can be done unconsciously, but this is not a healthy diet and that person is not aware that he is dieting. However, if he realizes this, the first thing he should do should be to consult a psychologist. Because both conscious or unconscious diets are psychologically harmful.

4. Diet Programs That Affects Psychology Positively

In this article, from the very beginning, the bad aspects of diet that affect psychology have been mentioned. However, there are positive affects of diets either. We can give many examples of the positive effects of diet. However, if we start from the simplest, we can say that the first reason is the satisfaction and happiness of reaching the desired body.

Our body is our appearance. For this reason, if we don't love our body, it means we don't love our house either. It means that we do not live comfortably and happily in our home. However, if we make this house the way we want, we will feel mentally safe and happy. Our body is just like that. If we love and like our body, we can feel more peaceful and happy psychologically.

One of the important effects of diet on psychology is that it gives psychological energy and enlightens the mind. Diet is not just about losing or gaining weight, but the main goal is to do it in a healthy way. Therefore, people on social media should not be trusted. Healthy diets affect people psychologically in a positive way. Thanks to your new and healthier eating habits, you can easily feel better.

The way to be happy starts with eating habits. If a person constantly has fast food or similar unhealthy eating habits, this creates negative effects on both his appearance and psychology. If we consider this physically, we can easily say that especially fast and unhealthy weight gain,

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slowing of metabolism and many other similar negative things. However, when I consider this spiritual situation spiritually, the situation is a little different. This is because this situation is confusing in every way.

According to the statements of experts, fast food is very popular around the world. And when people do the things they love, they release the hormone of happiness. From this, it can be concluded that people are happy when they eat their favorite food. However, when you constantly eat fast food or the same type of food, there will be no excitement or special side, and your brain does not secrete this hormone anymore because it has become a habit. At this time, people resort to dieting. Both to lose the weight they gain from eating fast food all the time and to feel good by living healthy. Finally, thanks to the healthy diet program prepared and given to the person, the brain begins to secrete the hormone of happiness again.

In short, our brain can trick us into feeling good when we eat unhealthy food, even if we do it lovingly. But this does not apply to healthy things. Because the positive effects of healthy nutrition on the body are visible enough to be seen, and this makes people feel good.

In addition, people have a desire to be constantly satisfied by their nature. Regardless of the age range, people want and do it. There may also be cases where this is not done consciously. People who can do this consciously or unconsciously of this need for satisfaction become a little selfish over time. In particular, the person on a diet may show that he is eating healthy by unknowingly belittling others in order to satisfy himself psychologically. While this creates happiness in that person, it creates a feeling of not understanding in other people. However, when the psychology of that person is taken into consideration, the person will feel better psychologically, since the need for satisfaction is satisfied.

In fact, everyone who is on a diet has done behaviors that will affect their psychology in a positive or negative way, even if they are not aware of it. But the important part here is to be a little patient. Because you can feel bad when you are in diets, of course, if you do not compare yourself with other people, you will not have such a problem.

When we evaluate according to what is written in the article, the other factor that we can count among the psychological positive factors affecting the diet will be perseverance and patience. As a requirement of human nature, once he is satisfied with something he has earned and worked for, he begins to do this constantly. In other words, when you see the positive effects

of the diet, you will continue to do it and as a result, you will achieve what you want, your goal. When we examine this psychologically, this state of being ambitious by seeing others gives that person determination, stability and, if he has left, the excitement of starting that job again. In other words, dieting can also help the person in a positive way. After the last positive result, the person starts to use this determination, stability and patience for other areas as well.

5. Getting Rid of Diet Psychology

Going into diet psychology negatively affects a person's health in every way. It does this both psychologically and physically. Let's start with the psychological effects which starts the diet first;

a.) Feeling Unqualified

Feeling inadequate is found in almost all mental illnesses. While this feeling of inadequacy can sometimes cause a direct disease, it can sometimes progress a disease. It is natural to feel inadequate, especially when you are on a diet, but situations such as its progression are not very healthy. Feeling bad about people with the body you want, or having thoughts that you can never have this physique even if you want to, are among the symptoms of feeling inadequate. We can also use the term to feel inadequate, such as feeling worthless.

In short, when you realize that you are comparing yourself to other people, it means that you have already put yourself into the psychology of feeling inadequate. If this comparison is negative, you should know that you have a symptom of depression. You can also fall into thoughts as if you are below average when you feel inadequate and at the same time worthless. In fact, feeling inadequate when looked at includes a long period of time that can go back to childhood. However, it would not be correct to make an inference that it only occurs in childhood. Even the reasons people start dieting are sometimes just because they feel inadequate when they compare themselves to other people.

Inadequacy is a really bad feeling. Because when you experience the feeling of inadequacy and worthlessness, you start to question the subject you are most confident about, even your

most confident feature or ability. For example, for a person who thinks he is good at losing weight and considers it normal for his progress to be slow or fast, a person he cares about may create a feeling of inadequacy, even as a joke.

b.) Bullying people for their weight

Especially in adolescence, high school people bully each other a lot. And they don't feel comfortable with it as a conscience. However, it can have great psychological effects on the people they bully. In general, bullying is done about the body, so I will give such an example. The bullied person may resort to unhealthy diets because of bad words he heard from a person who is underweight because he is overweight.

This also applies to people who are extremely thin. In fact, people do not realize how much they affect each other's psychology. This situation is probably the thing that will make them stay behind for every society. Because if people in a society can hurt each other and they don't care about it, if they don't think about it, this can even bring their end. There are bullying situations in almost every society. These bullies prevent the person from loving themselves. It not only prevents him from loving, but also allows the person to turn to self-harming behaviors. There are too many people who start dieting because of bullying. People who apply to this diet for both weight gain and weight loss will always feel inadequate due to the effect of bullying on their psychology, no matter how much weight they gain or lose. They will always want more. And they will do it without realizing it. If this continues, help should be sought. In cases where psychological treatment is not provided, the situation can become serious and even lead to suicide. Which is undesirable.

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) has prepared a report called 'bullying in schools'. According to this report, 19 percent of students aged 15 and in this age group in Turkey are exposed to physical or verbal violence at least a few times a month by their friends or by people of the same age group.

In fact, if we do a little research, we see that people who bully often resort to bullying either because they have been bullied in the past or because they can't express themselves in the home, especially because they want to remove their anger from outside.

c.) The Perception of Beauty that Social Media Is Trying to Impress on People

Today, especially in the media and social media, the aesthetic perception of beauty, which is created and tried to be spread very quickly, can also cause aesthetic anxiety in women. In particular, it triggers conditions such as body dysmorphic disorder. Experts state that dysmorphic disorder revealed by social media may be unrealistic perceptions and expectations of the individual's own body. He recommends that people with these aesthetic concerns get expert support if they reach a level that will affect their daily life and reduce or restrict their social and professional functionality. In cases such as not being taken, diets that cause the body to be more unhealthy can be applied. Although these unconsciously applied diets enable the person to get the body they want, it is necessary to continue this diet to protect it and not to continue the diet in order not to deteriorate the health any more. However, in general, when people who apply to this diet realize that they have started to gain weight, they directly turn their unhealthy diets into a way of eating in their lives. Since these situations are very dangerous, if psychological support is not provided, it can cause great psychological and physical diseases that can lead to the death of the person.

As for these perceptions of beauty, the things we generally know are; blond hair, thin body, pronounced body lines, beautiful nose, full lips, etc. However, they are not needed to be beautiful. If a person loves his own body, it will be easier for that person to have a healthy body, since no one will care about his thoughts and will not be offended. Because they do not have thoughts such as risky diets or risky surgeries to lose weight. It is absolutely illogical to conform to the perception of beauty. Since the perception of beauty is a definite and clear thing, everyone conforms to the perception of beauty and no one is different from anyone else. If everyone becomes "Beautiful" so to speak, then there will be no concept of beauty. For this reason, the important thing is to know your own worth, to own and love your body,

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instead of trying to adapt to the perceptions that social media tries to impose on people, it will make you feel better.

This is how we can list the factors that cause unconscious diets. Of course there is more, but this is what we can say in general. Well, let's assume that for the reasons we listed in this way, you unconsciously started a diet before you were ready. When you start a diet, if you follow this diet, it can create psychological difficulties for you. Therefore, it is recommended that you first be psychologically prepared. It is recommended that people who are dieting should raise awareness about the processes they will experience before starting the diet. If they do not prepare themselves for what will happen in the diet and do not take them into account, they can wear themselves out psychologically. Many people complicate the weight loss process with thoughts such as what I will not eat, how long I will be hungry, instead of motivating themselves with suggestions such as I want to have a healthy diet, I want to be healthy, I want to lose weight, I will be in that body.

Diet psychology is a process that should be considered before starting a diet and it should be felt ready both physically and mentally. Not being able to lose weight can destroy you, you may think that you will not succeed, maybe you may not be satisfied after losing weight and you may want to lose more. That's why diet psychology is actually much more important than starting a diet. If you are not ready, you cannot continue. As a solution to this, in addition to the difficulties and gains to be experienced in the future at the beginning of the diet, if your goals are written side by side in a notebook and carefully examined, it can be realized that this is a great source of motivation and the problems that are thought to be experienced can be easily overcome. Whenever you experience low motivation, you can open this notebook and regroup your motivation.

In addition, another thing you can do to get rid of diet psychology is to have full willpower no matter what. Because the psychological effects while on a diet can push you to quit your diet in general. For this, you must learn to control your will before you start a diet. In our lives, there are thousands of diet lists that we can easily access about diet almost everywhere on the internet. You can choose from those prepared by healthy and real expert dietitians and start the application. The important thing is that the diet list you have decided to implement

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is healthy and that you have adjusted it according to how long you will stick to it. Or there should be a list that you can take from your daily life in harmony, otherwise you may put yourself under great pressure to follow the diet. It is an important item recommended for you to plan yourself before you start the list you intend to apply. When you start the application, providing that willpower, difficulty or ease varies depending on the list and program you choose. However, whether it is easy or difficult, what you need to do is to follow the list day by day and be patient.

In order to control willpower while dieting, it is important to set a realistic goal. When you start a serious diet for the first time in your life, starting with a difficult diet causes the diet to put psychological pressure on you. In order to protect yourself from this psychological factor that affects the diet, you should start easily and after you get used to it, you can gradually prepare yourself for more difficult diets. For example, if you do not have any interest in sports throughout your life, but you apply something similar in the program you have chosen, this program will not be a program that will benefit you much. It may be more logical to determine simple daily exercises that are suitable for you and to spend more productive time on these exercises. To point out a wrong point, as experts have also stated in the researches, being weighed every day will cause a loss of motivation for you. Since there is a change in your body and the structure of each body is different, some days you can give it as fat, some days it can be given as muscle, sometimes you can throw it out as edema. For such reasons, instead of being weighed every day, you can be weighed on a specified day of the week and, if possible, at the same time.

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